

Statement and Experimental Proposal on the Relationship Between Gravity and Illumination

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Original Statement and Experimental Proposal

Date: March 13, 2026

Statement of Belief

I, Paul Hautzinger, wish to place on record my belief that gravity and illumination (historically referred to as light) share a fundamental underlying relationship within the structure of the physical universe.

My observation arises from considering circumstances in which the Earth's surface remains illuminated even when the Sun itself is not directly visible, such as during heavy fog or cloud cover.

From these observations, I propose the working hypothesis that illumination may be directly related to gravitational interactions.

Hypothesis

I hypothesize that areas commonly perceived as sunlit may represent regions where the Earth is effectively illuminating itself in the direction of the Sun due to gravitational interaction.

Proposed Experiment

1. A wooden board will be prepared with a star-shaped cutout in the center.
2. The board will be positioned between the Sun and the Earth's surface.
3. The board will initially be held close to the ground.
4. The board will then be gradually lifted upward while observing the projected shape.

Predicted Observation

The edges of the illuminated region may begin to feather as the object is raised, and the projected shape may smooth toward a circular form.

Supplemental Statement of Hypothesis

Date: March 18, 2026

I, Paul Hautzinger, further clarify my hypothesis.

It is my belief that matter exhibits illumination in the presence of other matter, proportional to gravitational interaction.

The degree of illumination corresponds to the magnitude and interaction of gravitational fields.

This document records the author's belief and proposed experiment.

Signed: Paul Hautzinger

March 18, 2026